

OPTIMAL ASSIGNMENT OF PRECAST COMPONENTS TO MINIMIZE CURING COST

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Abstract:

Efficient production of precast concrete components is essential for transportation infrastructure projects, where strict schedule compliance and effective cost management directly influence project feasibility and contractor performance. This study develops a method to minimize the curing cost that effectively maximizes pallet capacity utilization during the curing process of precast concrete manufacturing. The model incorporates practical operational constraints, including demand satisfaction, mold availability, pallet dimensions, spacing requirements between components, weight limits, and labor-related loading and unloading costs, while allowing multiple component geometries to be arranged within a single pallet configuration. By dynamically adjusting pallet layouts across successive production cycles, the framework captures demand variability, resource limitations, and operational uncertainties inherent in real precast plants. The proposed approach improves pallet space usage, reduces unnecessary pallet cycles, lowers curing energy consumption, and minimizes labor expenses without compromising curing quality or structural performance. Validation using real-world industry data demonstrates measurable reductions in curing-related costs and significant improvements in overall resource utilization and production efficiency. Beyond the curing stage, the optimized pallet layout structures provide a systematic spatial foundation that can be extended to enhance mold placement during casting and improve storage layout planning after demolding. As a result, the model supports integrated decision-making across curing, mold utilization, and storage operations. The proposed framework offers a scalable, data-driven decision-support tool that strengthens precast production planning and enhances the reliability and efficiency of transportation infrastructure delivery systems.

Keywords: Precast concrete, Concrete curing, Pallet utilization, Layout optimization, Mixed integer programming.

Running Head: Optimizing precast components assignment in curing process.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Precast concrete (PC) components provide consistent quality, faster installation, and quicker construction because they are manufactured off-site. Many cost-effective methods exist for producing precast components, including design, material management, production planning, inventory control, transportation, and on-site assembly. Among these, production planning is especially important because it determines how resources are used to complete jobs on time and within the budget. However, many current planning practices rely heavily on the experience of planners, which can lead to inefficient use of resources and higher costs. Studies show that prefabricated buildings can cost about \$44–72 per square meter more than conventional cast-in-place construction, which limits wider adoption and has attracted attention from governments and researchers (Xue *et al.*, 2017).

1.1 Literature Review

A substantial body of literature formulates precast production planning such as flow shops or job shop scheduling problems (Chan and Hu, 2002) under realistic operational constraints such as mold-availability (Benjaoran *et al.* 2005). Then this work has been extended by Yang *et al.* (2016) to develop a multi-production-line flow shop scheduling model and applying genetic algorithms to improve scheduling efficiency. There are other researches which have optimized raw-material handling for precast concrete production by developing varying cycle times and also by developing optimal co-operative procurement policy for both precast material supplier and manufacturer (Mazumder and Sarker, 2025; Mazumder and Sarker, 2026a,b; Sarker and Mazumder, 2025). Several studies have dealt with different production stages of PC to minimize completion time and tardiness penalties (Ko and Wang, 2011) and also for maximizing the average pallet utilization rate for rectangular PC to reduce pallet cycles by developing mathematical models and algorithms (Wang *et al.*, 2018; Liang *et al.*, 2024). These studies mainly focus on single rectangular geometries while ignoring practical constraints such as mold availability, weight carrying capacity of pallets, spacing, labor costs, unmet-demand penalties, and demand variability, often assuming static conditions that do not reflect real manufacturing environments. Therefore, the *goal* of this research is to develop an optimized pallet-layout plan for the curing stage which considers demand fluctuations, weight limits, and resource constraints to achieve a more efficient and cost-effective precast production process. To achieve this goal a *specific objective* is set to find the optimal assignment of different PC components to minimize the curing cost by maximizing the average utilization rate of pallet capacity (e.g., area, space, etc.).

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

In most PC production shops, a single component is placed on each pallet during curing, leading to excessive energy use, higher labor costs, and longer curing times (Figure 1a). Inefficient pallet utilization (Figure 1b) increases the number of required pallets and pallet cycles which eventually delays production, and wastes resources. While for slow and fewer PC components production, this problem may not affect a company significantly, but for a high demand and frequent production of these PC components, the problem may be of significance both technically and economically. Since different layout configurations allow different numbers of components per pallet, optimizing component placement can reduce cost and resource consumption per unit while improving production efficiency.

Figure 1. Unused space on pallet during the curing process of precast components with various shapes.

Optimizing pallet-area utilization during curing can reduce costs, avoid delays, and improve sustainability in precast production, which is important for meeting modern transportation infrastructure demands. Meeting strict delivery deadlines for precast components is also necessary to avoid penalties and maintain good relationships with clients. Using pallets more efficiently during curing helps lower production costs and improve overall efficiency. This research focuses on finding the best way to arrange precast components on pallets before they are placed in the kiln for curing. The model aims to maximize pallet space utilization while considering the weight of different components and ensuring that customer demand is met. Proper allocation of components during curing also supports adequate curing time and conditions. In practice, manufacturers sometimes ship components before they are fully cured to meet urgent demand, which can reduce long-term durability.

3. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The purpose of current study is to minimize the curing cost of precast manufacturing process by ensuring highest possible utilization of the pallet-area ($L \times W$). Different types of patterns (p) will be considered before placing various types of PC components (i) in different operating cycles (o). The proposed objective (cost) function (f_Z) includes the energy used for curing the concrete in kilns during the total curing time (T^c) and the labor involved in loading and unloading these components with shortage penalty cost as well. The energy cost (\$) of curing manufactured PC components is $T^c E/b$ where E is energy consumption cost (\$/hour) and b is the kiln chamber capacity of holding pallets in every cycle. The loading/unloading cost in dollars is $\sum_i C_L a_{ip}$ where C_L is the labor cost (\$/components). The term, $[1 - \gamma(1 - A_p/LW)]$, adjusts this base cost according to pallet utilization, where A_p is total used area of the pallet. When utilization ($u_p = A_p/LW$) is low, the factor $(1 - A_p/LW)$ increases the effective cost, thereby economically penalizing inefficient pallet layouts. $\sum_i \pi_i S_i$ is the penalty cost associated with unmet demand. So, the formulated Optimal Assignment of Precast Component (OAPC) model aims at minimizing f_Z by determining optimal values of some decision variables such as number of PC type i placed during pattern p (a_{ip}), number of pallets using pattern p during cycle o (x_{po}) and unmet demand for PC type i (S_i).

$$\text{Min } f_Z(a_{ip}, x_{po}, y_{po}, S_i) = \sum_o \sum_p \left(\frac{T^c E}{b} + \sum_i C_L a_{ip} \right) \left[1 - \gamma \left(1 - \frac{A_p}{LW} \right) \right] x_{po} + \sum_i \pi_i S_i \quad (1)$$

Subject to,

(A) Production Planning Constraints:

- A1. Demand must be satisfied
- A2. Number of pallet is limited
- A3. Weight carrying capacity of pallet is limited

(B) Geometric Constraints:

- B1. PC components must fit within pallet horizontally
- B2. PC components must fit within pallet vertically
- B3. Two consecutive PC components can not overlap

The proposed problem is a mixed-integer programming (MIP) model along with these two types of constraints (Mazumder and Sarker, 2026b), jointly optimizes pallet layout assignment, curing operations, and production planning in precast concrete manufacturing, where a_{ip}, x_{po}, S_i are integer variables and y_{po} is a binary variable indicating whether pattern p is used in cycle o (1 if used in cycle o , or 0 otherwise).

4. Results and Discussion

The OAPC model is evaluated using an industrial case study reported in Wang *et al.* (2018), which documents the curing and pallet layout operations of a precast concrete manufacturing facility, referred to as Plant A. The original study provides real plant production and layout data, which has been used for validating optimization approaches to pallet layout and curing planning in make-to-order precast production with a fixed production horizon. This study aims at optimizing pallet layout configurations and pallet cycling decisions to reduce production cost and improve curing efficiency. To solve this, a two-stage MIP-based algorithm is developed: the first stage applies column generation to add cost-improving pallet layouts,

and the second stage enforces integrality and operational constraints through the final mixed-integer master problem.

4.1 Findings

Table 1 shows that the proposed model fully satisfies demand with zero unmet quantities by selecting 10 patterns and cycles, while reducing the total curing cost to approximately \$17,428. Figure 2 illustrates how the model balances pallet utilization, pallet count, and pallet weight across production cycles while satisfying all component demands.

Table 1. Convergence of proposed MIP model and optimal value of f_z .

CG Round	LP Objective (\$)	Total Patterns	Slack Types	Total Slack
1	13,500,394	8	7	1127.00
2	4,763,716	12	4	394.00
3	1,435,274	20	2	100.00
4	810,138	32	1	53.00
5	516,636	36	1	39.00
6	17,428*	45	0	0.00
7	45,786	47	0	4.00

* Represents the row consisting optimal result of proposed MIP model

Table 2 represents the production plan across ten curing cycles. In each cycle, the model selects a specific pallet pattern and repeats it using a certain number of pallets to produce different combinations of precast component types. Pallet utilization remains consistently high (about 74%–94%), indicating efficient layout usage. Early cycles use larger pallet counts to address higher demand, while later cycles require fewer pallets as remaining demand decreases. Overall, the results show that demand is satisfied through sequential pattern selection and pallet repetition while maintaining high pallet utilization.

Table 2. Cycle-by-cycle optimal production plan from industrial case study.

Cycle	Pattern ID	Number of used Pallets	u_p (%)	PC Types in Pattern (a_{ip})
1	9	21	91.3	{1: 2, 8: 2, 3: 4}
2	1	21	73.8	{4: 5}
3	8	22	91.5	{1: 2, 4: 1, 3: 3, 6: 1}
4	21	22	89.6	{2: 2, 7: 4}
5	29	22	93.0	{5: 3, 1: 1, 3: 2, 6: 1}
6	26	22	93.9	{5: 3, 4: 2, 7: 2, 3: 1}
7	17	21	89.9	{1: 2, 4: 1, 6: 3, 3: 2}
8	20	19	93.7	{2: 2, 3: 3}
9	19	22	91.3	{2: 2, 8: 2, 3: 1}
10	23	14	88.6	{5: 3, 4: 2, 3: 1, 6: 1}

Across all cycles, the consistent use of mixed-component patterns plays a key role in achieving high utilization. Patterns combining multiple component types, such as in Cycles 1,3,5,6,7,9 and 10, allow smaller or lighter components to fill residual spaces around larger elements, improving area usage without significantly increasing pallet weight.

4.2 Discussion

The proposed model produces stable and high-utilization layouts across heterogeneous production cycles, while dynamically adjusting pallet count and weight to respect operational limits. In these cycles, the model selects mixed-component patterns that efficiently fill pallet space while keeping total weight-carrying capacity within allowable limits. This balance is critical in precast manufacturing, where excessive pallet weight can disrupt handling and curing operations even when geometric space is available.

Figure 2. Optimal pallet layout patterns for the industrial problem.

Finally, the collective outcome across all cycles highlights the integrative nature of the optimization approach. Demand satisfaction is not achieved in isolation within individual cycles but emerges from the coordinated interaction of pattern selection, pallet repetition, and cycle sequencing over the entire planning horizon. Each cycle contributes incrementally to meeting the total demand, and the cumulative effect of these decisions results in complete demand fulfillment without activating penalty terms or requiring additional curing capacity.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that integrating curing operations into a structured optimization framework provides tangible benefits for both production efficiency and long-term infrastructure performance. By explicitly linking pallet layout decisions, curing capacity constraints, and cost considerations, the proposed Optimal Assignment of Precast Component (OAPC) model offers a systematic approach to improving the consistency, reliability, and economic viability of precast concrete production. This model improves the durability of construction and transportation infrastructure projects by optimizing the curing process to ensure uniform curing, consistent strength, and structural integrity of precast components. Uniform curing reduces defects like cracks or voids, thereby increasing the lifespan and resilience of infrastructure elements such as roads and bridges. Additionally, the model promotes energy efficiency and effective labor utilization during the curing process, preventing rushed jobs and ensuring that each component meets high quality standards.

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